

PREFERRED TEACHING METHODS BY MEDICAL AND DENTAL STUDENTS OF A PRIVATE UNIVERSITY: THE STUDENTS' PERCEPTION

Anthony Leela*, Deputy Dean(FOM), Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, AIMST University, Kedah, Malaysia

Co-Authors

- (1) **Swe Swe Latt**, Senior lecturer, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, AIMST University, Kedah, Malaysia.
- (2) **Tahminah Afrose**, Lecturer, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, AIMST University, Kedah, Malaysia
- (3) **Inn Kynn**, Former lecturer, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, AIMST University, Kedah, Malaysia.

**Corresponding author*: Anthony Leela, Department of Community Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, AIMST University,

Abstract: Teachers need to change the approach of teaching to integrate classroom teaching by not only acquiring knowledge, but also developing critical thinking and clinical reasoning. Thus, changes are needed from the old didactic teaching. To maximize student learning, a diversity of teaching styles and a variety of methods are also needed by utilizing the present technology. This study explored the students' attitude towards the effectiveness of current teaching methods and the preferred method that gave them maximum benefit of their everyday life.

A cross sectional study was carried out among 324 third and fourth year medical (204) and dental (120) students in a private medical university using a self-administered questionnaire to assess their preferences on current teaching methods. The chi-square test was carried out to elicit association of various socio demographic factors and the different types of classroom teaching. Independent samples t test was used to measure between medical and dental students' attitude towards different teaching methods. The overall results of students' attitude towards effectiveness of current teaching methods were highest in video (75.1%) followed by questions (70%), problem based learning (PBL) (69.6%), discussion (69.3%), case study (67.2%), lecture (66%), power point presentation (PPT) (65.9%), quiz (60.4%), group work (56.4%), role play (49.2%) and debate (43.3%) respectively. Dental students have significantly higher mean score differences in preferences on video (0.54), PPT (0.33) and lecture (0.28) and medical students have higher mean score differences in preferences on discussion (0.34), quiz (0.50) and debate (0.30) with $p < 0.05$. Around one third of the students' choice of best method was the standardized lecture slides with proper learning outcomes and well explanation by the lecturers. The study suggests that to shift our teaching strategies from didactic traditional teaching and recommend a combination of other methods like PBL, videos, quiz and discussions to cater the needs of the adult learning and also to make it more interesting, interactive and effective.

Keywords: Educational environment, teacher-centered, student-centered, teacher-student interaction, effective teaching methods, classroom learning, Interactive method, e-learning.

1. Introduction

Health care professionals, medical and dental doctors are expected to provide safe, compassionate and competent health care to the patients¹. Their role is complex, they need to make important decisions and demands high critical thinking and clinical judgment compared to decades ago². The teachers/trainers need to prepare for the health care sector students to meet these demands in the competitive world where patients are exposed to internet and question the doctors and even sue them if any untoward event occurs.

One of the important components of classroom learning is the social and communicative interactions between student and teacher, and student and student (peers). The student should have the ability to ask questions without fear, share an opinion, agree or to disagree, challenge the teachers and these are fundamental learning activities. It is through these methods and through discussions, debate, interactions, a new concept can be formed, and the learning objectives be achieved. An old method and assumption can be challenged, and a new idea or method can be formed.

Teaching methods have changed over the years from the normal traditional didactic teaching to various other methods like problem based, role play, small group teaching, group discussions, quiz-game etc. Students especially from the health care sector need higher level of critical thinking for clinical judgement skills and patient care. Teaching and learning for health care

professionals is highly complex and diverse and thus it is essential to use innovative methods to improve class room teaching and student learning.

Teachers need to change the approach of teaching to integrate classroom teaching by not only acquiring knowledge, but also developing critical thinking and clinical reasoning. Thus, changes are needed from the old didactic teaching³. To maximize student learning, a diversity of teaching styles and a variety of methods are also needed by utilizing the present technology. This study explored the students' attitude towards the effectiveness of current teaching methods and the preferred method that gave them maximum benefit of their everyday life⁴.

2. Methodology

A cross sectional study was carried out among 324 students with third and fourth year medical (204) and dental (120) students in a private medical university using a self - administered questionnaire to assess their preferences on current teaching methods in June to August 2017. The participation is voluntary, and a written informed consent was obtained before the survey. All registered year 3 and year 4 students from medical and dental faculties were purposively chosen as they have some knowledge and percepts of class room teaching after having three to four years spent in the university. The exclusion criteria were students who are in year 1, 2 and year 5. The year 5 students were not included as they are not staying in the campus and it will be difficult to get them.

The questionnaire is divided into two parts: section A contained questions on socio demographic factors such as age, sex, ethnicity, faculty, year of study in this university and in section B, there were questions on the types of class room teaching and their preferred methods.

In the section B of the questionnaire, the participants can choose on each types of teaching learning methods such as video show, question, problem based learning (PBL), discussion, case study, lecture, lecture with power point presentation (PPT), quiz, group work, role play and debate based on their perceptions as *not effective/ somewhat effective/ neutral or no opinion/ effective/ very effective*. Finally, the results were divided into two categories/ groups only as group 1. *somewhat effective/effective/very effective* and group 2 was the combination of *not effective and neutral* for categorical data analysis. For numerical data analysis, the results were scored to recode as (0= *not effective*, 1= *neutral*, 2= *somewhat effective*, 3= *effective*, 4= *very effective*). The independent variable was the socio demographic factors which include age, gender, ethnicity, faculty. The dependent variables were the type of class room teaching methods.

3. Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 22. The demographic data (age, sex, ethnicity, faculty, year of study) and students' preferred methods were shown with the descriptive statistics as frequency/ percentage and preferred methods by different faculties was shown with multiple response analysis too. The chi-square test was carried out to elicit association of various socio demographic factors and the different types of class room teaching. Independent samples t test was used to measure the association between medical and dental students' attitude towards different teaching methods.

4. Ethical approval

This proposal was submitted to and approved by the Ethical Committee of the University.

5. Results

There were 324 number of students who were participated voluntarily in this study among them 204 students were from the medical faculty and 120 students were from the dental faculty. The mean age and SD of the students was 22 years (0.8), with female (61%) and male (39%). Among them the year 3 medical students were 104 (32%), followed by the year 4 medical students 100 (31%), the year 3 dental students 72 (22.2%) and the year 4 dental students 48 (14.8%) respectively. Most of them were Chinese 209 (65.7%), Indian 96 (30.2%), Malay 6 (1.9%) and others 7 (2.2%).

The overall results of the students' attitude towards effectiveness of current teaching methods were highest in video show (75.1%) followed by questions (70%), problem based learning (PBL) (69.6%), small group discussion (69.3%), case study (67.2%), lecture (66%), power point presentation (PPT) (65.9%), quiz (60.4%), group work (56.4%), role play (49.2%) and debate (43.3%) respectively and the overall results were also shown with multiple response feedback analysis too. (Table 1 and picture 1)

The dental students were preferred video show (87.4%), followed by PPT (71.4%), lecture (71.4%), PBL (70.6%), case study (68.1%) to other teaching methods. The dental students have significantly higher mean score differences in preferences on video (0.54), PPT (0.33) and lecture (0.28) with p values <0.05. (Picture 2, Table 2)

The medical students were preferred discussion (74.5%), questions (72.5%), quiz (66.5%), group work (57.5%), debate (48.5%), role play (51%) to other methods compared to dental students' preference. The medical students have higher mean score differences in preferences on discussion (-0.34), quiz (-0.5) and debate (-0.29) with p values <0.05 too. (Picture 2, Table 2)

The results of the association between gender (male & female) and preferred teaching methods were PPT (56.5% & 70.6%), lecture (60.9% & 68%), case study (75.7% & 61.7%), questions (69.6% & 70.6%), group work (54.4% & 55.9%), quiz (63.5% & 57.3%), discussion (73.9% & 65.4%), video (75.7% & 75.8%), debate (46.1% & 41%), PBL (71.1% & 68.9%) and role play (44.3% & 50%) separately. The female students were preferred PPT to other methods compare with male (70.6% & 56.5%) and it was significantly difference with p= 0.014 and male students were preferred case study to other methods (75.7% & 61.7%) with significant difference of p=0.013. (Table 3)

Finally, the overall one third of the students recommended preferred best method and it would aid them in maximum benefit of learning was "*standardized lecture slides with proper learning outcomes and well explanation by the lecturers*".

6. Discussion

The second main aim of the basic medical education is to develop an attitude to learning that is based on curiosity and the exploration of knowledge rather than in its passive acquisition⁵. The teachers need to help the students to take responsibility of their learning, support and facilitate them. However, teachers are using the traditional didactic teaching but there should be more interaction between the teachers and the students and incorporate new ideas⁶ and collaboration with multiple teaching methods with students participation⁷. Effective teaching can be judged by the progress and high achievement of the students even though there are many other factors like the student and teacher characteristics. One of the ways of assessing effective teaching of teachers is by feedback from students and their peers⁸.

In this study the students gave the feedback on their current teaching methods and their preferred methods as follows:

Learning/ teaching via video show

The students' attitude towards effectiveness of learning with video show was 75%. Video show is the combination of audio and visual aids (watching the steps to perform) and listening too. It is good for clinical teaching in the larger groups as well as the smaller groups by using film of patients with different clinical presentations. It is useful for teaching communication skills and practical skills to the students and the students can keep films for self-appraisal.

In this study the dental students were preferred on video show because in dental faculty, some lecturers conduct lectures and practical sessions by using video shows. But it is not compulsory, however, it is of lecturers' preference. If deemed necessary, and if it gives better explanation lecturers do include videos in their lecture presentations. In most of the dental practical classes lecturers included videos either downloaded from you tube or few videos prepared by lecturers themselves. In medical faculty, some lecturers are also using video show for basic terminology introduction, communication skills, ethical issues, different presentations of a case, performance skills, doctor-patient relationship and let the students to critically appraise and make group discussion based on video show and to present it before end of the section.

Learning /teaching via Problem-based learning

The students' attitude towards effectiveness of problem-based learning was 70%. PBL is used in many medical schools in the UK and worldwide. The students use 'triggers' from the problem case or scenario to define their own learning objectives and made discussion among group members. PBL is not only for problem solving but also to increase knowledge and understanding. The group learning facilitates communication skills, teamwork, problem solving, independent responsibility for learning, sharing information, respect for others⁹.

The three major principles are involved in the process of PBL guided by the facilitators: i. required a certain level of background knowledge, ii. the case is real and is in a relevant context of learning, iii. discussion with peers, facilitators, specialists of the subject¹⁰. In PBL, the students have to make group discussion based on the provided case scenario and finally they may get the combine knowledge on different contexts of the subjects.

Lecture (teaching large group)

The students' attitude towards effectiveness of lecture was 66%. Lecturing or large group teaching is one of the oldest forms of teaching. Lecturers are transferring knowledge and concepts to large groups. It is to stimulate interest of the learners, explain concepts of the context of learning, provide core knowledge and direct student learning. It tends to encourage passive learning of the students but little opportunity to critically appraise the new knowledge offered¹¹. All lecturers must be carefully planned, structured and well-prepared students learning outcomes (SLO) to show the students before starting the lectures and conclude the key issues as a summary. Lecturers give the opportunity for the learners to ask questions before the end of the lecture¹².

Small Group Discussion (SGD/ SGT)

The students' attitude towards effectiveness of small group discussion was 66%. When small group teaching works well, it allows students to discuss/negotiate meanings, express themselves in the language of the subject and establish closer contact with lecturer. It also improves the skills of listening, presenting ideas, persuading, and working as part of a team to the students. *'The value of effective group management in professional development and lifelong learning cannot be underestimated'*¹³. With a good topic and a skilled leader, small groups can provide a stimulus of learners' discussion directed towards specific objectives of the learning¹⁴.

PowerPoint presentation (PPT)

The students' attitude towards effectiveness of PPT was 66%. The female students preferred PPT to other methods compared with male (70.6% & 56.5%) and it was significantly difference with $p=0.014$. The ability to make the computer-generated slides has transformed the way that many people create teaching materials as one of the educational tools¹⁵. It is to highlight key points or reinforce what the facilitator is saying; it should be short and to the point include only key words and phrases for visual reinforcement. It is generally used at large groups and lecture formats as visual aids. Lecturers should be careful on template design, transitions, animations, slide shows, font size, font color, back ground color of the slide, bullet and numbering, number of line/sentence words in a slide depend on the ppt rules and regulations. But the problem of providing PPT to the students was they are totally relying on that slides and students do not read text books and references. The students are answering the exam questions based on PPT slides and they do not describe about the contents. It is the drawback of providing PPT to students.

Regarding case-study and quiz, the clinical students preferred to learn bed-side teaching with case-study, enjoy communicating with the patients and have discussions with lecturers. For quiz, this university started to introduce quiz-game as Kahoot! to all faculty students and their feedback on quiz-game was very effective for their learning process too.

In summary, most of the students requested their lecturers *"standardized lecture slides with proper learning outcomes and well explanation by the lecturers"*. It was heightened on the teaching experiences of the teachers too.

So for the lecturers, the five core propositions of the teachers should be able to do for the learners are: teachers are committed to students and their learning, know the subjects they teach and how to teach those subjects to students, responsible for

managing and monitoring student learning, think systematically about their practice and learn from experience and teachers are members of learning communities too. To stabilize this proposition it is an indication of the teaching profession's ability to create and maintain a body of knowledge that guides practice along with the roles of technology and language play in students' lives¹⁶.

This study was done in only one private medical and dental university with small volunteered samples so that it cannot be represented to all students' perceptions from health care sectors of all universities in Malaysia.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Constructive and alternative teaching methods promote students' active participation. A blend of teaching styles helps the students acquire in-depth knowledge. The 21st century teachers are responsible for students with a diverse range of learning abilities. They must apply effective teaching methods focusing on general students as well as slow-learning students and those with attention deficit tendencies. Laptops and tablets, video conferencing, group discussion, problem solving discussion, case study, e-learning in classrooms play a vital role in today's teaching styles. This is mandatory for the 21st century teachers to apply the modern technology and assess their students' knowledge while they are learning.

This study suggests that to shift our teaching strategies from didactic traditional teaching and recommend a combination of other methods like PBL, videos, quiz and discussions to cater the needs of the adult learning and also to make it more interesting, interactive and effective. The teachers must find out the effective teaching methods that work best for their students. Knowing how to engage the students by trying different teaching methods will help the teachers to find ways to reach each student.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Aimst University Malaysia for permission to collect data and publication. Our gratitude to all medical and dental students and Deans of both faculties and team members who involved in this research.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest in this study.

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Annex

Table 1. Health Professional (medical and dental) Students' perception on the current teaching methods at Aimst University (n= 324)

Different teaching methods	Somewhat effective/ effective/very effective N (%)	Not effective/ neutral N (%)
Video	241 (75.1)	80 (24.9)
Question	226 (70)	97 (30)
Problem based learning (PBL)	224 (69.6)	98 (30.4)
Small group Discussion	223 (69.3)	99 (30.7)
Case study	217 (67.2)	106 (32.8)
Lecture	214 (66)	110 (34)
Power point presentation (PPT)	213 (65.9)	110 (34.1)
Quiz	194 (60.4)	127 (39.6)
Group work	181 (56.4)	140 (43.6)
Role play	158 (49.2)	163 (50.8)
Debate	139 (43.3)	182 (56.7)

**Table 2. Mean score differences on preferences of different teaching methods
Coding (0= not effective, 1= neutral, 2= somewhat effective, 3= effective, 4= very effective)**

Different teaching methods	Dental students Mean score	Medical students Mean score	Mean score difference	P value
Video	2.97	2.43	0.54	0.001*
Case study	2.48	2.37	0.11	0.413
PBL	2.43	2.37	0.06	0.651
PPT	2.43	2.1	0.33	0.012*
Lecture	2.42	2.14	0.28	0.031*
Question	2.33	2.52	-0.19	0.138
Discussion	2.19	2.53	-0.34	0.01*
Quiz	1.9	2.4	-0.5	0.0003*
Group work	1.84	1.88	-0.04	0.790
Role play	1.67	1.78	-0.11	0.40
Debate	1.43	1.72	-0.29	0.038*

* P value significant at < 0.05

Picture 1. Multiple Response Analysis of Students' perspective on different teaching methods

Picture 2. Preferred teaching methods between medical and dental students

Table 3. Association between gender and preferred methods of students

Different teaching methods	Male %	Female %	P value
PPT	56.5	70.6	0.014*
Lecture	60.9	68	0.212
Case study	75.7	61.7	0.013*
Questions	69.6	70.6	0.856
Group work	54.4	55.9	0.804
Quiz	63.5	57.3	0.293
Small group Discussion	73.9	65.4	0.123
Video	75.7	75.8	0.97
Debate	46.1	41	0.391
PBL	71.1	68.9	0.694
Role play	44.3	50	0.344

* P value significant at < 0.05